

“ASSESSMENT OF FACTORS OF LOW ACHIEVEMENT OF ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING IN LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN SOME ADVENTIST AND PROTESTANT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN GOMA

BALUME KAMARO GENTIL

balumekamaro@gmail.com

Institut Supérieur Pédagogique de Rutshuru « ISP Rutshuru »

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to investigate the factors that have led to the low achievement of teaching and learning of English in listening and speaking skills through out some Adventist and Protestant secondary schools in Goma. Therefore, the current study contributes to enable EFL teachers and students to find out important factors which they need to apply for a holistic education of English to happen within their schools. I have used qualitative and quantitative methods to gather reliable and consistent data from 10 teachers and 100 learners the targeted schools. The results prove that all respondents including school officials have shared responsibilities that led to inefficient education of English and which resulted in low achievement of learners in English especially in listening and speaking skills. In a special way teachers are submitted to various deficiencies which have worked as barriers that have impacted inefficiently their teaching goals. This situation has pushed most of learners to view English as a black beast and as a tough language unable to be grasped and mastered. So, certain suggestions are proposed to enable teachers to provide an effective teaching that would enable students to improve positively their listening and speaking skills.

Keywords: English, teaching and learning, listening and speaking skills, low achievement.

INTRODUCTION

This section describes the background relating to the study, objective of the study, research questions, scope and significance of the study.

Background to the study

Effective teaching and learning of English is a great challenge in several countries of the world and in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Undoubtedly, there is urgent need for qualified and effective teachers to enable efficient teaching to take place in DRC secondary schools in general and in Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary Schools in particular.

Teaching activities in some Adventist and Protestant Secondary Schools of Goma are confronted to serious challenges which have hindered more teachers from offering a reliable teaching of English language to each of their learners. Some teachers employ bad teaching strategies and lack updated teaching resources. Furthermore, they lack reliable visual aids, language laboratories, and adequate facilities that can enable

them to teach English appropriately to their learners by enabling them to improve their listening and speaking skills efficiently.

There are obviously many differences among the students all over the world. Concerning to the background differences, the students also have different attitudes in the classroom. Thomson (2005) says that some teachers find that their students are often busy talking and chatting among others and do not concentrate on the listening subject. In listening students need full concentration on the audio being played, otherwise they may not catch the messages from the audio. Some students have low motivations because they are forced to be in the class and because they are not willing to learn. Some of them have problem on concentration and find listening is more difficult than other subjects. Students simply turn off when listening to spoken English as it is seem too difficult follow without high level of concentration.

According to Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985), learners could learn best by exposure to comprehensible input which was slightly beyond their current level competence. Krashen (1985) pointed out that second language learning was similar to first language acquisition, thus listening was the first step on the way to language proficiency. Similarly, in his Total Physical Response, Asher (1977) stated that oral language was primary to written language and listening comprehension should precede speech production. He also emphasized that learners were supposed to listen and obey the orders given by the instructor through actions.

Nunan (1997) calls the listening skill as the 'Cinderella Skill' which is overlooked by its elder sister speaking in language learning. Listening received little attention in language teaching and learning, because teaching methods emphasized productive skills and listening was characterized as passive activity (Richards&Renandya, 2010). However, researchers have revealed that listening is not a passive skill but an active process of constructing meaning from a stream of sounds. Listening can be considered the fundamental skill to speaking, because without understanding the input at the right level, any learning cannot begin. Listening is the process of receiving, constructing meaning from and responding to spoken and/or non-verbal messages (Brownell, 2002). Listening is an active, purposeful process of making sense of what we hear (Helgesen, 2003). Listening comprehension is a highly complex problem-solving activity that can be broken down into a set of distinct sub-skills (Byrnes, 1984). According to Underwood (1989), listening is an activity of paying attention to and trying to get meaning from something we hear (p. 1). In the same vein, Mona & Bahman (2017) define listening as a complex cognitive process which entails the ability to correctly receive and interpret intended meaning hidden in the communication process (p.33).

As far as communication skill is concerned, many educationists such as Wallace (1982), Richards (2006), Gebhard (2006), Harmer (2007), Aggarwal (1996, 2003),

Brown (2000), Krashen (1981), Richards and Schmidt (2010), Tembue (2006), etc. have spotted various deficiencies in English teaching that hinder communication. According to them if language teaching and learning fails to promote communication this is due to some deficiencies in it.

Wallace (1982) makes it clear that some teachers plan out excessive teaching materials in their lessons that they are unable to cope with in a single lesson. He points out that planned materials are too excessive in theory but too short in practice. Equally important is that teachers seem to forget the two teaching principles of TTT (Teacher Talk Time) and PTT (Pupil Talk Time) that Gebhard (2006) and Harmer (2010) term 'Teacher Talk Centrality'. This means that the teacher should talk less than his students during a particular lesson in order to increase their communicative competence. In the same connection, Harmer (1991) highlights the benefit of devising adequate input that generates adequate output. According to him, exposing students to language input is not enough. Teachers need to provide opportunities for learners to produce language they are able to select from the input they have received. Ur (1988) and Patel and Jain (2008) assert that the quality of input plays a tremendous role in learners' language acquisition.

In addition, there is a challenge of non-involvement of most of the targeted teachers in self-development as it has been advocated by Harmer (2007), Gebhard (2006), etc. Most of these EFL teachers never seek to enhance their teaching development by learning new things about the new orientations of the language teaching process. Following these educationists, teachers should be involved in both 'intensive' and 'extensive' reading which can open them to broad horizons in new teaching methods and methodologies for successful teaching. Richards (2006) on his part claims that teachers should use more communicative language teaching for it has become the most teaching approach in English language teaching and learning today. It advocates among its several principles the integration of skills which consolidates the practices of English learning (Harmer 2010).

Problem

Providing effective teaching of English in Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary Schools is valued as major concern in the mind of the teachers. However, many of these teachers have been undergoing more challenges which have hampered their teaching and their students learning activities inefficiently. They do resort to poor teaching strategies which have hindered most of their students from appropriating their teaching, and are not equipped with sufficient teaching resources which can enable them to provide a holistic education of English to their learners. In addition, they create a tough learning environment on behalf of learners by imposing them to use a correct English while they are unable to do that.

These challenges have pushed many learners to consider their teachers as incompetent and unprofessional thus they were encouraged to hate their teaching. Instead of using English at school, they interact in French language which they easily speak and Swahili language considered as their mother tongue. They do perceive English as a very tough language which can neither be mastered nor grasped. These problems have also created complex learning environment for the students and have been pushed to hate English and develop at the same time a negative attitude against it. Furthermore, they have occasioned inappropriate consequences on their overall performance in this language because many of them are unable to listen, to speak, to write and to read English clearly. Therefore, it is in this particular context where I have chosen to make an investigation of deficiencies that have contributed to the low performance in listening and speaking skills of students in English within Adventist and Protestant Secondary Schools in Goma by carrying out this study entitled; “Assessment of factors of low achievement of English teaching and learning in listening and speaking skills in some Adventist and Protestant Secondary Schools in Goma”.

Objective of the Study

The main objectives of this study were to:

- i. Find out the main causes of students low performance in English listening and speaking skills within some Adventist and Protestant Secondary schools in Goma.
- ii. Explore the challenges that the teachers recruited in the envisaged schools do encounter throughout the fulfilment of their duty.
- iii. Provide reliable suggestions that should lead for the improvement of both teaching and learning activities of English language in these schools.

Research Questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the following questions:

- a. What are causes of poor improvement in English among the envisaged learners?
- b. Are there difficulties that hamper inefficiently the teaching of the targeted teachers?
- c. How should learning and teaching expectations be enhanced in these schools?

Scope of the Study

The study targeted the assessment of major factors that led to low performance of English teaching and learning in listening and speaking skills throughout the targeted schools. It was conducted via five schools from which the following were Adventist; Institut Maranatha and Institut 2 Injili while the following were

Protestants; Institut Metanoia, Institut Hekima and Institut Hermoni. I was interested by various criteria for their selection mainly; having minimum of good infrastructures, engagement of qualified teaching personnel, offering good education which is appreciated in the region, discipline proved by their learners, and good ratio of success of the previous years' learners on the national examination.

Significance of the Study

This study is useful for the targeted teachers, because it would guide them to be in acquaintance with useful recommendations that should facilitate them to perform their teaching activities which would enable pupils to perform their learning goals as well. In addition, this study is important because the information that it contains, would push other researchers to conduct further—research oriented in this appropriate field, through other schools in order to discover additional results.

1. Review of Literature

There are many causes of poor performance in English language among some Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary learners. These include the followings: The dominance of French and Swahili known as the mother tongue are regarded as one of the cause of poor performance in English language. Usman, (2012) was of the view that all students are surrounded by a complex linguistic situation that force them to learn their first indigenous language and they are required to have a good command of the English language. The ministry of EPSP translated in English as the ministry of Primary, Secondary and Professional teaching and known in French as “Enseignement Primaire Secondaire et Professionnel”, of Democratic Republic of the Congo teaching policy, does not impose the teaching of English language at primary school.

Swahili language is used as the immediate language of the community in the eastern part of the country and in Goma. It is officially taught at primary school differently from English language which is officially taught at secondary school. Basically, the policy recommended the use of French and Swahili languages to be used in teaching curriculum at primary school. This situation contributes immensely in poor learning of English language which starts at secondary school. Fema, (2003) was of the view that; the major cause of the errors in English used by Nigerians can be attributed to the interference of mother tongue with the English language. He added that learners often use their native language or mother tongue in all their interactions and English is only used within the four walls of the classrooms and ends there.

Similarly to this idea, the dominance of French and Swahili languages in the targeted schools, had contributed immensely in poor performance in English language. In addition, the issue of some inexperienced and competent teachers of English, also

contributed to the poor performance in English language in some of Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary schools. Due to the above mentioned causes, in some schools other subject teachers are forced to teach English language and some who even read it exhibit poor abilities in oral and written expression of it. Therefore, with this kind of situation those teachers cannot teach effectively and hence poor performances from their products. Alluding to this situation, Adedokun, (2011) stated that poorly trained English and untrained teachers (of English) were employed to teach and prepare secondary school students for the school certificate examinations in English language. This situation contributed immensely in poor performance in English language among secondary school pupils.

Therefore, it is clear that some inexperienced teachers of English in some Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary schools, lead to poor performance in English language. Inadequate infrastructural facilities and total lack of instructional media are regarded as another cause of weak performance in English language in those targeted schools. Roger, (1981) was of the view that instructional materials and facilities are important part of the process of learning as they provide practice and feedback in learning track.

Currently, in some of the targeted schools, pupils are in most of cases sitting in bad conditions because of large size in numbers without sufficient desks to fit them. In some cases, pupils are making much noises and that unfriendly behavior is creating a complicated environment of leaning and which in many cases affects negatively their learning of English language. In addition, even where there are enough classes, they are overcrowded and language laboratories are absent as it is the case in most of secondary schools of the country and North Kivu Province schools in general. All these cannot allow for proper learning of English language, hence lead to inefficient performance. Sa'ad (2007) was of the view that teaching and learning take place effectively when classes are moderate.

Some classes of the envisaged schools are overcrowded with more than 50 pupils per classroom, and this cannot allow for proper teaching and learning to happen effectively. Furthermore, in the area of instructional resources or media, there is dominance of textbooks, syllabuses constituted by the teachers alone. In addition, there are few school dictionaries which are sometimes used to check the meaning of new words. Modern media such as audio, video tapes, language laboratories, programmed texts, flash cards; computers, magazines and newspapers are never nor rarely used. Mohammed, (1998) observed that the teaching of English language is bedeviled with many problems such as; inadequate period of teaching, method of teaching and lack of adequate and useful resources. Therefore, no wonder that, the inappropriate infrastructural facilities leading to large class sizes and inappropriate as well as obsolete teaching resources, lead to low performance in English language in the targeted secondary schools.

Another important cause of poor performance of English language in these schools, is the teachers' attitude toward innovation and use of instructional media. Most of the targeted teachers, fail to take into account the dynamic nature of English curriculum but they continued to bore pupils with definitions and drills in grammar, vocabulary and speech work. They still practicing very much the traditional content/knowledge oriented teaching. In this regard Abdullahi, (2003) was of the view that teachers mostly prefer to use traditional ways of teaching which they have been familiar with or as they were taught, which do not necessarily aid proper learning. Ya'u, (1993) categorically said that successful achievement of stated objectives in teaching and learning is always associated with using the right technique. Therefore, poor attitude of these teachers relevant to innovation and use of instructional media or materials in teaching English language, do lead to ineffective performance of teaching and learning English language in these schools.

Another important cause of ineffective performance in English language is the negative attitude of pupils toward the learning of English language. Many pupils show negative attitude toward the learning of English language because they consider it foreign or not theirs. The fact that they have challenges of grasping even French language accurately which is an official language of teaching, they regard English as a tough language with negative perception as well. Mohammed, (2002) was of the view that most students put a kind of negative attitude in learning and use of English language as well as making teachers task a difficult one indeed. It is obvious that for any pupil to be proficient in English language, mastering of skill of listening, speaking, writing and reading is necessary, and it requires a hardworking and commitment from the pupils. Henceforth, it is obvious that the negative attitude of learners toward learning English language is one of the essence and engine of their inadequate performance in this language.

Improper use of teaching methodology also causes low proficiency in English language learning among the targeted school pupils. It is totally believed that effective teaching and learning take place when accurate teaching methods are implemented by the teachers. Ya'u, (1993) in Sa'ad, (2007) was of the view that successful achievement of stated objectives in teaching and learning is always associated with using the right method. In many cases teachers of English language from the targeted schools do not consider parameters linked to the learners' age, the topic, the time and background of the learners in choosing the method to be used in teaching and this affects the level of learning of the learners. Therefore, based on these authors viewpoints, it is obvious that there are various challenges which impact ineffectively the teaching and learning goals of English in various countries including the DRC and Goma secondary schools in particular.

2. Methodology

This section was based on research design of the study, population of the study, sample for the study, sampling technique, instruments for data collection, reliability of the Instrument.

2.1. Research Design

The design that I used in this study was descriptive survey. It was used because it permitted me to study small sample and later generalized the findings to the whole population. Osuala, (2001) was of the view that in survey research small sample is studied and the findings generalized to the population.

2.2. Population of the study

The population of this study was all learners studying in some Goma Adventist and Protestant Secondary schools and all teachers of English recruited therein.

2.3. Sample for the study

The sample used in this study was hundred pupils and ten teachers selected using stratified random sampling technique, in which hundred and fifty pupils and fifteen teachers were selected.

2.4. Sampling Technique

I used stratified random sampling technique in selecting the sample for this study. This is because it permitted me to have representation from both the teachers and pupils.

2.5. Instruments for Data collection

I used a questionnaire as an instrument for the collection of data for this study. The questionnaire comprised of various items on the variables of the study. The response format of "Yes" or "No" was used in the instrument. In addition, I also used interview as an instrument for the gathering of data in order to trap out various viewpoints of the respondents regarding the phenomenon under study.

2.6. Reliability of the Instruments

According to Mugenda (1999), reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument is consistent in giving same results after repeated trials. Concretely, the reliability on this study was observed in the following ways; I selected the sample purposively on the specific area. Then I used a checklist of

questions when I was making interview with respondents in order to achieve data correctness and completeness.

3. Data Analysis Procedure

The data collected were analyzed using frequencies and simple percentages.

3.1. Data Presentation and Analysis and presentation of the Results

This section was based on presentation and analysis of the data gathered from the respondents as well as the results. In this section below, I used the following Table 1 to gather various data collected from the targeted learners regarding main causes that contributed to their poor performance in English.

Table 1. Main causes of poor performance in English language among learners from the targeted schools.

N0	Questions	Frequencies			Percentages		
		Yes	No	Total	Yes	No	Total
1	Do you always appreciate to speak English more than French and your Swahili when you are at school?	30	70	100	30%	70%	100%
2	Does the use of French and Swahili at school contribute to your ineffective learning of English language?	92	8	100	92%	8%	100%
3	Are there clear visual aids and relia instructional materials used by your teachers when they are teaching?	35	65	100	35%	65%	100%
4	Do your school facilities help you to study in favorable environment?	41	59	100	41%	59%	100%
5	Are your teachers enough experienced and competent to teach English?	60	40	100	60%	40%	100%
6	Do your teachers use adaptable teaching methods which help you to appreciate their teaching?	43	57	100	43%	57%	100%
7	Are there English language teaching laboratories in your schools?	0	100	100	0%	100%	100%
8	Do you feel motivated to listen, speak, write and read English every day?	77	23	100	77%	23%	100%

Source: Field survey 2023

In table 1 above, it is clearly seen that 30% of the respondents proved that they always do appreciate to speak English more than French and Swahili when they are at school. However, the great majority (i.e 70%) of these respondents say that they do not always appreciate to speak these languages more than English when they are at school. 92% of the respondents have rightly answered that the use of French and Swahili at school does contribute to their inefficient learning of English language

while 8% of respondents have revealed that the usage of these languages does not contribute to their inefficient leaning of English language.

(35%) of the respondents have confirmed that they teachers do not use clear visual aids and relia instructional materials throughout their teaching in order to enable them grasp their teachings, while (65%) of the respondents have affirmed that their teachers do use clear visual aids and relia instructional materials to enable them grasp their teachings (cfr. question 2). To the third question, 41% of the students have answered that their school facilities do help them to learn in peaceful environment whereas the big majority (i.e 59%) of the students have proved that their school facilities do not facilitate them to study in good environment (cfr. question 4). To the fifth question, (60%) of the respondents have answered that their teachers are enough qualified and competent to teach English while (40%) of the respondents highlighted that their teachers are not enough qualified and competent to teach English.

To the sixth question, 43% of the students have responded that their teachers apply adaptable teaching methods that help them to grasp their lessons while the great number (57%) of the learners affirmed that their teachers do not adapt their teaching methods to their intellectual capacity to enable them to grasp their lessons. The great majority (i.e 77%) of the respondents have affirmed that they do not feel motivated to listen, speak, write and read English every day while (23%) of the students have proved that they do not feel motivated to listen, speak, write and read English every day (cfr. question 7). Finally, (100%) of the respondents have answered that there are no language laboratories in their schools which can contribute to the enhancement of English teaching and learning activities. In this section below, I used the following Table 2, to gather various data collected from the targeted teachers regarding the challenges which impact impact inappropriately their teaching.

Table 2. Difficulties which impact unsuccessfully the teaching of the targeted teachers

Question	Responses	Frequencies			Percentages		
		Yes	No	Tot	Yes	No	Tot
What are difficulties which impact your teaching unsuccessfully?	Lack of language laboratory in our schools which can help to prompt effective teaching	10	0	10	100%	0%	100%
	Lack of school visual aids and sufficient teaching materials	8	2	10	80%	20%	100%
	Some overcrowded classrooms with most number of learners	7	3	10	70%	30	100%
	Lack of parental involvement in pushing learners to do their home assignments and read their notes	7	3	10	70%	30%	100%
	Lack of pupils' strong commitment in	8	2	10	80	20	100%

	learning						
	Lack of in-training services to upgrade our teaching skills	10	0	10	100%	0%	100%
	Little time allocated to English teaching and learning	10	0	10	100	0%	100%
	Lack of good salary wage factor	10	0	10	100%	0%	100%

Source: Field survey 2023

The data provided in Table 2, reveal clearly that (100%) of the respondent teachers have answered that the challenges which affect inappropriately their teaching can be justified by lack of school language laboratories which can help them to prompt effective teaching. To the second response, (80%) of the teachers have confirmed that their inappropriate teaching of English is justified by the fact of lacking school visual aids and sufficient teaching materials, while (20%) of the targeted teachers did not provide answers accordingly. To the third response, a big majority (i.e 70%) of the respondents, have proved that the challenge of overcrowded classrooms does impact inefficiently their teaching of English, while (30%) of the respondents did not provide their responses accordingly. To the fourth response, the great majority (i.e 80%) of the respondents have mentioned that lack of parental involvement in pushing learners to do their home assignments and to read their notes at home does impact negatively their teaching, whereas (20%) of the respondents have remained silent regarding this question.

To the fifth answer, the highest number (i.e 80%) of the respondents have mentioned that their teaching is impurely affected by the lack of learners learning motivation, while a feeble number (i.e 20%) of respondents did not respond anything accordingly. (100%) of the respondents have mentioned that their teaching is abused by the fact of lacking in-training services which must help them to upgrade their teaching skills (cfr. response 6). In the same logic, (100%) of the respondents have mentioned that their teaching is hampered by the problem linked to a little time allocated to the English course (cfr. answer 7). (100%) of the respondents have proved the fact of being paid meaningless salary impacts negatively their teaching (cfr. answer 8). The following section, enabled me to gather various answers that the targeted learners had provided regarding important factors which they ought to apply in order to help them to perform their learning goals.

Table 3: Factors that can help the performance of English learning among students from the targeted schools

N0	Questions	Frequencies			Percentages		
		Yes	No	Total	Yes	No	Tot
1	Are you determined to make personal efforts in order to listen and speak English in your daily activities so as to enhance your learning skills in this language?	93	7	100	93%	7%	100%

2	Do you think that the recruitment of qualified and competent teachers of English can help you to perform your learning skills in English?	75	25	100	75%	25%	100%
3	Do you think that an adequate use of teaching methods by your teachers can motivate you more and more to appropriate their teaching?	100	0	100	100%	0%	100%
4	Can the implementation of language laboratories in your schools contribute to the amelioration of your English learning success?	96	4	100	96%	4%	100%
5	Are you convicted that doing effectively your home works can contribute proficiently to your learning skills in English?	91	9	100	91%	9%	100%
6	Can the organization of English various debates in your schools push you to perform your learning skills in English language?	81	19	100	81%	19%	100%

Source: Field survey, 2023

In table 2 above, it is overtly seen that the highest majority (i.e 93%) of the responds of students have answered that they are determined to make personal efforts in order to listen to English and speak it within their daily activities for the enhancement of their listening and speaking skills, while (7%) of respondents have mentioned that they are not determine to make any efforts to improve both skills in this language. To the question 2, a great number (i.e 75%) of the respondents have proved that the recruitment of qualified and competent teachers of English can help them to perform their learning skills in English whereas (25%) of the respondents have revealed that such a recruitment of quality of that teachers, cannot lead them to enhance their learning skills. (100%) of the respondents of learners have answered that an adequate use of teaching methods by their teachers can progressively motivate them to appreciate English (cfr. question 3).

To the fourth question, the greatest majority (i.e 96%) of the respondents have responded that the implementation of language laboratories in their schools can contribute to the amelioration of their English learning skills, while a weak number (4%) of the respondents have confirmed that the implementation of language laboratories in their schools cannot contribute to the improvement of their English learning skills. The great majority (i.e 91%) of the respondents have proved to be convicted that doing effectively their home assignments can contribute proficiently to their English listening and speaking skills, while (9%) of the respondents have proved not to be convicted that doing effectively their home assignments contribute proficiently to their English listening and speaking skills enhancement (cfr. question 5). Finally, (81%) of the respondents have revealed to be convicted that the organization of English debates within their schools can enable them to promote their English listening and speaking skills, while (11%) of the respondents have

answered that the organization of English debates within their schools cannot push them to perform their English listening and speaking skills.

4. Discussion of the Findings

The current section is centered over the discussion of the results. As demonstrated via various analyses above, it is evident that the targeted teachers have presented deficiencies which have corrupted enormously their teaching and consequently have hampered the leaning goals of the learners. Data have proved that these challenges increased by their teachers have served as barriers that discouraged students from enhancing their listening and speaking skills effectively, and thus were led to hate and neglect it English. The second language learning skills are namely; listening, speaking, writing and reading. However, this study is focused over listening and speaking skills. Most of students have demonstrated their unhappiness vis-à-vis inefficient teaching techniques which are used by some teachers and which do not help them to enhance effectively their learning skills especially listening.

Teachers should always remember that listening is one of the key strategies for assimilating knowledge. According to Mendelsohn (1998), it is imperative to listen. It is therefore their duty to resolve all inappropriate teaching approaches which have undoubtedly corrupted the listening and speaking skills of the students. They have to renovate their teachings especially by creating learning contextual situations with which students are familiar in order to facilitate them play their learning role effectively and, thereby helping them to become self-regulated. That manner of doing will widen more their understanding and maximize their learning about the subjects as well. So, they must always keep in mind that students listening and speaking skills in the classroom ought to be developed and shaped intentionally in order for them to be improved. Furthermore, these teachers have to be provided with proper teaching and visual materials that will facilitate them to motivate students to listen. In this context, the findings agree that students be submitted under numerous strategies of teaching by creating also a peaceful leaning environment for their best way of learning.

As a professional teacher of English, I have remarked that resorting to reading loud teaching approach offers students with an opportunity to boost their listening competences, and most of informants have regularly ben using it in teaching listening. According to Barrentine (2000) and Sipe (2000), reading aloud to children builds and supports their listening abilities and enhances their overall language development. The targeted teachers have to employ it when speaking, making repetition and during dictation in the classes, to permit students to understand and develop their listening skills as they clearly hear the different terminologies they encounter. Teachers should also focus more on communication approach by talking less while encouraging students to talk much so as to acquire proficiently their

speaking skill. This position copes with the statement of Magdalena Aleksandrak (2011:38), who was of the view that, Nowadays, in spite of the inevitable criticism of available methods, techniques or resources, speaking is generally perceived as the most fundamental skill to acquire.

Though achieving proficiency in foreign language learning skills in classroom conditions is not an easy task due to the fact that most of learners often finish a language course with the conviction that they are not sufficiently prepared for speaking beyond the classroom, findings via (Table 3. question 3), have shown that these learners, want to see language laboratories being implemented in their schools. They cope with the viewpoint of Abdelaziz M (2017), who wrote that, the developments in language laboratories are now apparent as access moves from a fixed network and related Microsoft operating systems to the online and browsers. Students can now access and work from these new cloud labs from their own devices at anytime and anywhere. Students can interrogate, record audio and video files; and be marked and assessed by their teachers remotely. Furthermore, (Slobin, 1985, p. 1164), added that, the only linguistic materials that can figure in language production are stretches of speech that attract the child's attention to a sufficient degree to be noticed and held in memory. So, it is most vital that school officers think deeply and plan of how to make the implementation of language laboratories effectively in their schools to facilitate students to be connected to the new technological gadgets that will help them to learn new things capable to boost the targeted skills in English.

Another main challenge which has highly corrupted the achievement of these students in the targeted skills in English, is their connectivity to the employment of Swahili and French languages which they speak even at school more than English. This attitudes endorses Ur (1995: 121), viewpoint who had evoked that, there are problems which are commonly observed in the language classrooms which are related to individual learners' personalities and attitudes to the learning process and learning speaking in particular. They cooperate with the inclusion of the Mother-tongue use - that is particularly common in less disciplined or less motivated classes, where learners find it easier or more natural to express themselves in their native language. So, these teachers have to resolve this challenge by first of all gaining confidence providing a holistic and attractive education of English. In addition they ought to motivate all learners, especially those who are weak in English to appreciate English and start speaking it regularly regardless of utterance errors which they are to undergo.

The challenge which relates to the lack of the organization of debates in English in the targeted schools has been regarded as another serious factor that has hindered these students from performing effectively the targeted skills. The findings on Table 3. Question 6) have proved that, they urgently long to see these debates being organized so as to grant them with ample time to practice English. They are sure

that, though they have been studying English as Foreign Language (EFL), for more years, their skills proficiency in this language is still poor especially in communication aspects (listening and speaking skills). According to (Slobin, 1985, p. 1164), this problem, somehow, is due to the little practice they do perform during their lessons. Therefore, students need intensive activities to attract them to practice listening and speaking in and out of their classes. In this regard, these teachers have to action accordingly in order to organize these activities so as to increase English knowledge of these learners.

5. Suggestions

As it has been proved through the results of this study, in order to perform the teaching and learning activities of English in listening and speaking skills in the targeted schools, the following suggestions should be applied:

- ✓ Implementation of language laboratories for the efficient teaching and learning to happen.
- ✓ Reinforcement of participative and interactive teaching methods by the targeted teachers.
- ✓ Putting much emphasis over creation of debates to promote pupils' learning aptitudes in English language with an intention of minimizing the effect of French and Swahili languages.
- ✓ Effective provision of varied visual materials for instruction.
- ✓ Construction of adequate minimum facilities for excellent teaching and learning to occur.
- ✓ Recruitment of competent teachers submitted under an employment test coordinated by professional teachers of English and Inspectors.
- ✓ Organization of in-training services by the education officials for the benefit of these teachers.
- ✓ Involvement of each learner in learning activities under the initiation of adequate learning environment.
- ✓ Building self-esteem aptitude in every pupil' mind to gain up their confidence and friendship.
- ✓ Motivate ceaselessly all pupils to listen and speak English at school and out of school yard regardless of their uttered errors.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this research, it was detected that there were evident factors which had contributed to the low achievement of English teaching and learning in listening and speaking skills among great number of students from some Adventist and Protestant secondary schools in Goma. Certain of the targeted teachers were not; (1) provided with sufficient teaching equipment (books and visual materials) to

facilitate them accomplish their duty properly, (2) offered language laboratories, (3) helped to work in good conditions because due to inappropriate facilities of their schools, (3) offered significant salary, (4) capable to arouse the consciousness of most of pupils to esteem English language appropriately, (5) able to apply adequately their teaching methods.

In addition, the results led to the conclusion that most of learners were confronted to major challenges such as; (1) some unexperienced teachers (2) hatred increased against English and lack of self-risk taking in order to learn it as they did in French language, (3) Usage of French and Swahili languages at school rather than English. Henceforth, I had proposed useful recommendations that should facilitate for the improvement of teaching and learning goals in the targeted schools. This study was designated as an exploring study that was definitely focused on gathering, analyzing and mixing qualitative and qualitative data with an objective of gaining deepest understanding of the phenomenon understudy. Numerous data were gathered in feedback to the questionnaire that was distributed to the respondents, and documents were consulted to collect qualitative data.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, M. (2003). *The attitude of Science Teachers in the Use of Instructional Media*. In Kano Journal of Education. 2 (1): pp 30-33.
- Adedokun, A. O. (2011). *Notes on Language Linguistics (Phonetics and Phonology) and English Language Method*. Ibadan: Fab Publishers.
- Asher, J. (1977). *Learning Another Language through Actions. The Complete Teacher's Guidebook*. Los Gatos: CA: Sky Oaks.
- Brownell, J. (2002). *Listening: Attitudes, principles, and skills (2nd Edition)*. Boston: Allynand Bacon.
- Byrnes, H. (1984). The Role of Listening Comprehension: A Theoretical Base. *Foreign Language Annals*, 17, 317-29
- Danladi, S. S. (2013). "Language Policy: Nigeria and the Role of English Language in the 21st Century". *European Scientific Journal*: 9 (17) pp. 1-21.
- Fema, B. M. (2003). *Problem of Teaching English Language in NCE Programme*. In Azare Journal of Education. 4 (1): pp. 107- 112.
- Harmer, J. (1991). *The Practice of English Teaching*. London: Longman Group UK Limited.
- Harmer, J. (2007). *The Practice of English Teaching*. London: Longman Group UK Limited.

- Helgesen, M. (2003). *Teaching listening*. In D. Nunan (Ed.), *Practical English Language teaching*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Gebhardt J.C. and O.R. (1999). *Language Teaching Awareness: A Guide to Exploring Beliefs and Practices*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Gebhardt J.C. (2006). *Teaching English as a Foreign or Second Language*. United States of America: University of Michigan.
- Kolo, A. I. (1992). *Essential of Research in Education (A Handbook for Students and Beginning Reseachers in Education)*. Lagos: Text and Leisure Publishers.
- Krashen, S.D. (1981). *Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.
- Krashen, S. D. (1985). *The input hypothesis: Issues and implications*. Addison-Wesley Longman Ltd. Addison-Wesley Longman Ltd.
- Mendelsohn, D., 1998, "Teaching listening", *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 18, pp.81-101.
- Mona, D, & Bahman, G. (2017). "The Effect of Pedagogical Films on the Development of Listening Skill among Iranian EFL Female and Male". In *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Learning*, Vol. 3, N°2, pp. 33-40. [Doi:10.5923/j.jall.20170302.01](https://doi.org/10.5923/j.jall.20170302.01)
- Mohammad, A. Y. (2002). *Promoting Children Language and Communication Development For Successful Democracy and National Development*. A Paper Presented at the School Of Education National Conference, Federal College of Education, Kano.
- Mugenda, O. & Mugenda, A. (1999). "Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches." Nairobi: *African Center for Technology Studies*.
- Nunan, D. (1997). *Designing and adapting materials to encourage learner authonomy*. Harlow: Longman.
- Oluwole, D. A. (2008). "The Impact of Mother Tongue on Students' Achievement in English Language in Junior Secondary Certificate Examination in Western Nigeria". *Journal of Social Sciences*. 17 (1): 41-49.
- Odumah, A. E. (1987). *Nigerian English*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press.
- Osuala, E. O. (1985). *Introduction to Research Methodology*. Onitsha: African Fab Publishers.
- Patel, M.F. and Jain, P.M. (2008). *English Language Teaching (Methods, Tools & Techniques)*. Jaipur: Sunrise Publishers & Distributors.
- Underwood, M. (1989). *Teaching Listening*. London: New York: Longman.

- Richards, J. C. (2005). "Second thoughts on teaching listening". *RELC Journal*, 36, 85-92. doi: [10.1177/0033688205053484](https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688205053484)
- Roger, B. (1981). *An Introduction to Applied Linguistics, Approaches/Methods in Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Sa'ad, T. U. (2007). *The Impact of Domestic Responsibilities on the Academic achievement Of Married Women in Tertiary Institutions of Bauchi state*. Unpublished Med Thesis. Bayero University, Kano.
- Tembue, Z.O. (2006). *Positive and Negative Factors in Learning English in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The case of Primary Schools in Bukavu*. Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation. Lubumbashi: Université de Lubumbashi.
- Thomson, K. (2005) *Helping Teen to Listen*. BBC British council. http://www.teachingEnglish.org.uk/think/listen/teen_listen.shtml. (accessed 4th October 2017).
- Ur, P, 1995. *A Course in Language Teaching. Practice and Theory*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ur, P. (1988). *Grammar Practice Activities. A Practical Guide for Teachers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Slobin, D. (1985). Cross-linguistic evidence for the language-making capacity. In D. Slobin (Ed.), *The Cross Linguistic Study of Language Acquisition* (vol. 2: Theoretical Issues). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Wallace, M. (1982). *Teaching Vocabulary*. London: Heinemann Educational Books.
- Ya'u, M. Z. (1993). *A Study of the Implementation of the National Islamic Studies Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools of Bauchi State*. Unpublished Med Thesis. Bayero University, Kano.